

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
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USING AN ELECTRONIC APPLICATION FOR MANAGEMENT OF CHILDREN WITH
OBESITY IN PRIMARY CARE

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Background: Obesity affects one in five children and adolescents in the United States (CDC, 2022). Children who suffer from chronic obesity are at a higher risk of becoming adults with obesity. Chronic obesity in children is associated with comorbidities such as metabolic diseases, heart disease, bullying, and low self-esteem. Current clinical weight management strategies are designed to promote the consumption of fruits and vegetables while increasing active play to reduce obesity rates among children. The development of technology has increased the number of electronic applications geared toward managing adults' wellness. Children have grown up with technology and can use it with ease. The literature is limited as to the use of electronic applications as tools in weight management for children to track their healthy behaviors.

Purpose: Assess the effect of implementing an electronic application geared to school-age children for weight management. **Methods:** Participants were children from 10–12-year-olds without co-morbidities. Participant variables measured included body weight, BMI, BMI%, waist circumference, self-esteem, intake of fruits, vegetables, and water, and electronic application use. **Results:** 14 of the 18 participants completed the project. There was an increase in body weight and BMI with a decrease in waist circumference. The self-esteem scores were stable throughout the project. Overall, there was an increase in fruit and vegetable intake. Daily exercise minutes increased post-intervention among all participants. **Conclusion:** The project's Start Simple with MyPlate (SSMP) electronic application for weight management successfully decreased waist circumference, which may have been an indication of visceral fat loss.

Keywords: Children, obesity, weight management, MyPlate diet, Start Simple with MyPlate electronic application, body weight, BMI, waist circumference, and self-esteem.

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Background

The prevalence of obesity has steadily increased in the U.S., likely due to societal diet and lifestyle changes over time. National surveillance data report that 18% of children are diagnosed with obesity that effects one in five children in the United States (Bradwisch et al., 2020; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2022a; Fryar et al., 2020; Ogden et al., 2018; United States Preventative Services Taskforce [USPSTF], 2017). Children who suffer from chronic obesity are at a higher risk to become adults with obesity. Obesity is defined as having a body mass index (BMI) above 95% (USPSTF, 2010). The BMI is calculated by taking a person's weight and dividing it by their height squared (USPSTF, 2010).

The physical complications of obesity can lead to the development of chronic diseases such as metabolic disorders, heart disease, joint disorders, and sleep disorders for a child later in life (Bradwisch et al., 2020; O'Conner et al., 2017; Umer et al., 2017). Additionally, obesity in children is associated with mental health disparities such as victims of bullying, low self-esteem and poor quality of life (Colpan et al., 2018; Fields et al., 2021; Hammar et al., 2019).

Despite the efforts to address obesity through traditional weight management strategies, the obesity rates continue to rise (Fryar et al., 2020; Ogden et al., 2018). There are multiple interventions available for weight management including technology-facilitated applications. The literature has identified that electronic applications are aimed at promoting healthy diet, tracking daily food intake and exercise to impact BMI, and weight. Although there has been a rapid growth in electronic application to assist in weight loss, there is limited research related to their effectiveness specific to children.

Statement of the Problem

The data from the Pediatric Primary Care (PPC) clinic used in this project showed a similar trend in overweight/obesity among children as noted in the nation. Examining the yearly averages between 2018 to 2021, follow-up visits for children diagnosed with overweight or obese had an increase from 25.8% to 50.7% in the PPC clinic. The influx of weight management visits affects the number of physical exams scheduled, which affects the PPC clinic economically. Additionally, the PPC clinic lacked universal provider guidelines for obesity management. Each provider used their preferred guidelines to manage and treat children diagnosed with obesity. Obesity management for patients and families in the PPC clinic typically consisted of a brief diet education and promotion of active play. The diet education included a verbal explanation to increase daily intake of fresh fruits and vegetables, lean proteins, and water, while limiting high-sugar beverages and junk food. The families and patients were advised by providers to exercise daily through active play, sports, and outdoor activities.

Purpose Statement

The aim of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) quality improvement project was to assess the effect of implementing an electronic application on school-age children's weight management. In addition, the project was implemented to augment knowledge about weight management and the effects on participants' self-esteem, nutrition, and exercise.

Supporting Framework

The Plan, Do, Study, Act model is used in organizations to continuously evaluate an implemented change (Langley et al., 2009). The model has been used for Quality Improvement (QI) projects in various healthcare institutions (Institute for Hospital Improvement, 2022). A QI cycle consists of four phases: Plan, Do, Study and Act (PDSA). John et al. (2014) successfully

implemented the PDSA model in 29 outpatient clinics to develop strategies for children diagnosed with obesity to standardize the processes used for their diagnosis and management. The PDSA model (Figure 1, Appendix A) shows that a QI cycle starts by clearly defining the aim. The actions and processes that will help with achieving the aim are identified and monitored; this includes identifying the variables that will be used to measure the aim. The hypothesis is tested, and the effect of the actions and processes are evaluated to assess effectiveness of the intervention (Langley et al., 2009). Finally, decisions are made about moving forward based on the outcomes achieved. The PDSA is a robust and flexible model that can be used across multiple disciplines to improve the quality of care. The model relies on expert knowledge from members of the organization who are aware of resources and how they can be best applied to ensure that a specific process is being followed (Langley et al., 2009). Each phase of the PDSA model is briefly described in the following section.

The Plan Phase

The Plan phase is the initial phase in the model where problem identification occurs. The next phase is to gather information regarding the background and causes of the problem to plan possible solutions (Brassard & Ritter, 2018). In this phase, a team can use a variety of tools to facilitate the identification of the specific problem and plan targeted solutions. Such tools include using the SMART format, fishbone diagrams, run charts, and theoretical models. The SMART format provides a structured way to identify the specific aim to ensure it is realistic, measurable, and achievable in a timely manner. The fishbone diagram enables teams to analyze and display contributing sources of influence on the problem. Run charts are used to evaluate the magnitude of the problem. The theoretical model such as Information-Motivation-Behavioral Model (IMB)

can be used to provide a structure and support to the conceptualization of the improvement process (Figure 2 in Appendix B).

The Do Phase

The Do phase is the second phase of the PDSA model in which a team trials the interventions to resolve the identified problem (Langley et al., 2009). Experts recommend implication of the trial phase in a small group over a short period of time (Brassard & Ritter, 2018). The Do phase focuses on learning about all unexpected events that may arise from the trial. A small trial can confirm or disprove a hypothesis (Langley et al., 2009). Specific tools that may keep the testing phase on track and allow for continuous observation of data include Gantt charts, checklists, and/or control charts (Brassard & Ritter, 2018).

The Study Phase

After conducting the Do phase, the data collected must be analyzed to evaluate if the intervention was successful or not. The data variables to be measured would have been defined in the Plan phase. To evaluate trends in a QI project, control charts can be used to provide a visual representation of variable data over time. The control charts allow the researcher to follow trends in the data and to identify special causes that may be unexpected (Brassard & Ritter, 2018). Additionally, descriptive, and inferential statistics can be useful in analyzing data changes over time in a project.

The Act Phase

The fourth and last phase of the PDSA model is the Act phase. This phase requires that researchers reflect on the results of their interventions. The data collected is used to determine if interventions were successful. If the interventions did not provide the desired outcome, there is a need to change and revise the PDSA by starting over. However, if the desired outcome is

achieved, the interventions are applied to a larger group or implemented in the whole organization. During the Act phase, the variable data are continuously monitored for the sustainability of the intervention (Brassard & Ritter, 2018; Langley et al., 2009).

Application of the PDSA Model

The Plan Phase

The PPC clinic identified an increase in children diagnosed as overweight or obese. Overweight and obesity were defined by the CDC as having a BMI 85% and 95% or greater, respectively (USPSTF, 2010). The BMI was calculated by taking a person's height in inches and weight in pounds and then dividing the weight by the height squared (USPSTF, 2010). This DNP project utilized the PDSA model to implement a process to address the weight management of children 10 to 12 years old. The purpose of this project was to use the Start Simple with MyPlate (SSMP) electronic application as a weight management tool for children to decrease body weight, waist circumference, and BMI over a three-month period of implementation.

The fishbone diagram helped the project leader (PL) to identify the specific variables that affected each component of the problem. The fishbone diagram that was created for this project (Figure 3 in Appendix C) has four components that achieved the purpose of this project. The components were obesity education, environment, self-esteem, and technology. Retrospective data collected from the PPC clinic showed an increase in the number of office visits related to weight management from 25.8% in 2018 to 50.8% in 2021 (Figures 4, 5, 6, and 7 in Appendix D).

In this project, the IMB model (Figure 2 in Appendix B) provided conceptual support in the planning phase of the PDSA model to examine the relationships between digital motivation, digital information, and behaviors in children. The IMB model supports the relationship between

information and motivation to change health behavior (Fisher et al., 2003). According to Ratcliff et al. (2021), the results of the Health Information National Trends Survey showed that the use of digital technology in health care has increased in the United States. Patients seek health information online, interact with providers over electronic mail, and access health records via electronic health records applications (Ratcliff et al., 2021). Fleary et al. (2020) used the IMB model to increase adolescents' consumption of fruits and vegetables; the study concluded that consumption of fruits and vegetables is associated with the amount of information and motivation provided to adolescents. Moreover, Fleary et al. (2020) noted that providing additional information and motivation counseling changed adolescents' consumption of fruits and vegetables.

The Do Phase

The Do phase in this DNP project involved trialing the effect of using a digital application SSMP on weight management among children 10-12 years old. The SSMP was a free electronic application created by the US Department of Agriculture (USDA). It was based on the MyPlate diet which Michelle Obama and the USDA concurrently launched in 2011. MyPlate diet was based on dietary recommendations from MyPyramid, which defined the daily recommended servings of grains, vegetables, fruits, milk, and meats. MyPlate provided a pragmatic approach to keeping track of the daily recommended nutrients using a visual representation. MyPlate used a dinner plate to recommend portion sizes of different nutrients, such as half a plate of each meal should contain fruits and vegetables. The diet recommends switching to low-fat milk and drinking water instead of sugar-containing beverages. The goals of the MyPlate diet were to balance calories and increase the intake of healthy foods (USDA, 2011).

The plan was to obtain both participant assent and parental consent prior to starting the SSMP weight management project. The PL guided parents who consented for their child to participate in the project to download the SSMP application to their electronic devices. The application used the MyPlate diet, which was personalized to the patient's age and sex. The PL defined the personalized diet goals for the 10-12 years old child and set the goals to 1.5 cups of whole fruits, 2.5 cups of vegetables, 6 ounces of whole grains, 5 ounces of low-fat protein, and three servings of low-fat dairy per day.

The PL demonstrated how to navigate through the SSMP mobile application. The child participants were instructed to use SSMP daily to track their fruits, vegetables, grains, proteins, and dairy intake. The PL counseled on the MyPlate diet, which focused on the intake of fruits, vegetables, grains, protein, and dairy. Participants were asked to follow-up in person at four, eight, and 12 weeks to evaluate their progress and measure physiological data (body weight, waist circumference, and BMI).

In addition to the SSMP application, parents who consented to enroll their children received two text message reminders per day. The first text message was sent in the morning and served as motivation for exercise such as a video or exercise tip. The second daily text message was sent in the evening inquiring about how many items were tracked in the SSMP application for the day. Optional additional resources were provided for participants such as weekly support meetings with the PL. The meetings were used to discuss SSMP application concerns, diet, and exercise. The PL offered the weekly additional meetings, at no cost, every Thursday from 4 p.m. to 5 p.m. over Zoom, which is an online communication platform. The platform was free of cost. The aim was to provide participants with additional support with SSMP application, nutrition, and exercise to help retain nutrition knowledge and physical activity.

The outcome was measured with tracking the number of items consumed into SSMP, body weight, waist circumference, BMI, parent survey, and Rosenberg self-esteem scale. Physiological data (BMI, body weight, waist circumference), self-esteem, and parent survey were collected at the start of the project and subsequent visits at four, eight, and 12 weeks. Children whose parents declined to register and enroll their child in SSMP received traditional obesity management counseling from the provider.

The Study Phase

The Study phase of the DNP project involved the researcher collecting and analyzing the data. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze data trends and changes over time in the project. Descriptive statistics were used to describe the sample and project's variables (body weight, BMI, BMI% self-esteem, waist circumference, parent survey, and SSMP use). The variables were evaluated by calculating the averages and standard deviation. Inferential statistics evaluated and measured whether an intervention had significant changes on the dependent variables (body weight, BMI, BMI%, waist circumference, and self-esteem) in the study (Grove & Gray, 2019). A paired t-test helped to identify changes in the dependent variables (body weight, BMI, BMI%, waist circumference, and self-esteem) after implementing the project intervention (Grove & Gray, 2019).

The Act Phase

The final phase of the PDSA model required the researcher to reflect on the results of the interventions (Brassard & Ritter, 2018). The data collected allowed the PL to investigate whether the intervention succeeded (Langley et al., 2009). The physiological data, parent survey, and Rosenberg's self-esteem results were compared to previous in-person visits among the children. If the results did not produce a decrease in body weight, waist circumference, and BMI, and an

increase in self-esteem for the children using SSMP application, then the PDSA was revised and the system restarted. If the PDSA produced significant outcomes with a decrease in body weight, waist circumference, and BMI, and an increase in self-esteem, then the intervention would be adopted into the PPC clinic. Management would work with the PL to develop a guideline and train the remaining providers on using the SSMP application as part of obesity management. In addition, if successful, the PPC clinic would continuously collect and analyze data beyond the implementation of the project to ensure that the children are maintaining their weight loss. The details on this phase are further discussed in the Discussion section of the project.

Review of Literature

Overview

A review of literature was conducted to investigate the research regarding weight management among school age children using an electronic application. The review process focused on two topics: electronic applications used for weight management among school-age children and weight management in conjunction with self-esteem, COVID-19 impact, and co-morbidities. The databases explored were CINAHL Plus, PubMed, Google Scholar and Mendeley. Search terms used included a combination of “obesity,” “obesity prevalence,” “child,” “pediatric,” “youth,” “school-age,” “surveillance,” “nutrition,” “diet,” “weight,” “weight management,” “COVID,” “pandemic,” “technology,” “electronic application,” “mobile application,” “MyPlate,” “mental health,” “mental health prevalence,” and “self-esteem.” Mesh terms were also used in combination with the above search terms.

The literature search was limited to journal articles published within the last five years, except for landmark resources related to obesity in children and the Rosenberg psychometric tool (Rosenberg, 1965). Additionally, the reference lists of the selected research articles were searched for pertinent articles related to the topic under investigation. The selected articles for this review of literature included quantitative and qualitative studies with study designs such as descriptive, retrospective, and Randomized Control Trial (RCT) studies. All selected studies were published in English and were peer reviewed. In addition to the journal articles, professional organizations such as the CDC, National Health and Nutritional Examination Survey, Division Nutrition, CDC’s Physical Activity and Obesity, and United States Preventative Services Task Force (USPSTF) were explored for obesity related publications and guidelines.

The review of literature was based on the above-mentioned topics, which were used to guide the development of this quality improvement project.

The purpose of this quality improvement project was to assess the effect of implementing an electronic application to weight management and evaluate body weight, BMI, BMI%, waist circumference, self-esteem, parent survey, and SSMP use among school-age children diagnosed with obesity at one PPC clinic in Southern California.

Obesity Among School Age Children

Obesity is defined by the CDC as having a BMI of 95% or greater (USPSTF, 2010). According to national surveillance data, obesity rates have increased by 18% in children nationwide (Fryar et al., 2020; Ogden et al., 2018; National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion, Division of Nutrition, Physical Activity, and Obesity [NCCDPHP], n.d). Obesity affects one in five children and adolescents in the United States (Bradwisch et al., 2020; CDC, 2022a; Ogden et al., 2018; USPSTF, 2017). During the Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) pandemic, BMI rates doubled in children 6 to 11 years of age. Additionally, the prevalence of obesity increased in children and adolescents from 19.3% to 22.4% (Lange et al., 2021b). The pandemic limited access to healthy foods and prevented many children from engaging in outdoor activities (Tester et al., 2020). The American culture is derived from people of different countries, but with a commonality of the western diet. The American western diet consists of foods that are high in saturated fat, salt, and processed carbohydrates (CDC, 2022c; Garcia-Gutierrez, & Sayavedrab, 2022).

Children who suffer from chronic obesity are at a higher risk of becoming adults with obesity. Obesity rates have been on the rise in the United States, most likely due to obesogenic behaviors, which include changes to societal diet and lifestyle, which have become high in fat

and sedentary behaviors (NCCDPHP, n.d.). Moreover, obesity can be the result of genetic and environmental factors such as diet, exercise, sleep quantity, familial history, and medication use (Bradwisch et al., 2020; CDC, 2022a). Multiple researchers have targeted diet and exercise as impactful elements to obesity prevention (CDC, 2022a; Choi et al., 2021; Cueto et al., 2019; Franceschi et al., 2021; Norman et al., 2018). Diet and exercise tracking were reoccurring themes found in the studies reviewed. The methods used to measure weight and diet differed across studies; however, the findings were consistent in identifying the benefits of nutrition knowledge, diet tracking, and exercise (Allender et al., 2021; Brown, 2011; Epstein et al., 1990; Franceschi et al., 2021; Rageliene et al., 2021). Some studies looked at the parent and child dyad and the associations between weight management, diet, and exercise (Fields et al., 2021; Norman et al., 2018). While other studies used different methods of technology to motivate a healthy diet and promote exercise (Cueto et al., 2019). Additional studies concentrated on tracking diet and exercise to create accountability of daily habits of the child (Choi et al., 2021; Cueto et al., 2019; Franceschi et al., 2021). Some studies looked at child temperament and eating habits (Leung et al., 2016). Additional studies focused on community-based education of diet and exercise to improve obesity (Allender et al., 2021; Barkin et al., 2018). Currently, the prevention of obesity involves an increase in both the individual's activity level and their consumption of fruits and vegetables (CDC, 2022a; Polhamus et al., 2009). Yet, Americans are not consuming the daily recommended number of fruits and vegetables (CDC, 2022c; Merlo et al., 2020; Lange et al., 2021a; Lee et al., 2019).

Effect of Obesity on School Age Children

Effect on Physical Health

Obesity among children can lead to a plethora of co-morbidities affecting the body and mind (Bradwisch et al., 2020; Hollar et al., 2010). Some researchers found an association between obesity and education. They found that weight management programs can decrease weight and increase school standardized scores in children (Hollar et al., 2010). The physical complications of obesity can lead to the development of chronic diseases such as metabolic disorders, heart disease, joint disorders, and sleep disorders for a child later in life (Bradwisch et al., 2020; O’Conner et al., 2017; Umer et al., 2017). The cost of treating obesity-related diseases in the United States varies from \$34 to \$147 billion (CDC, 2022b; Fein et al., 2021). Chronic disease can impact a child’s physical development and mental health (CDC, 2020d). These are concerns that should be addressed while the child is still young and anticipatory guidance can be provided to prevent chronic obesity into adulthood.

Effect on Mental Health

Obesity in children is associated with mental health disparities such as victims of bullying, low self-esteem and poor quality of life (Colpan et al., 2018; Fields et al., 2021; Hammar et al., 2019). Children diagnosed with obesity have reported peer teasing and low self-esteem (Colpan et al., 2018; Fields et al., 2021). Low self-esteem is associated with emotional and behavioral problems, which would further impact a child’s learning and social development (CDC, 2022d; Colpan et al., 2018; Hammar et al., 2019). Mental health disparities among children diagnosed with obesity can manifest into chronic diseases in adulthood, if not addressed during childhood (Bradwisch et al., 2020). Obesity related co-morbidities among children can lead to an economic burden on them as well as the healthcare system. To combat obesity and its

potential to be associated with co-morbidities, it is important to understand how behaviors such as eating habits and exercise influence weight management and what are the best approaches to address it.

COVID-19 Impact on Obesity among Children

The COVID-19 pandemic affected the United States with additional barriers contributing to increased obesity rates. During the COVID-19 pandemic there were obstacles in acquiring nutritious foods and exercise. In March 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic urged people to stay home to prevent the spread of the disease, this prompted family to stock up on foods that had long shelf life which tend to be low in nutritional value versus fresh, nutritious food such as fruits and vegetables (Tester et al., 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic created barriers to exercise during the issued mandate to stay home to decrease the spread of the COVID-19 virus. The reduced exercise and isolation conditions contributed to weight gain but also to mental health disparities. Mental health disparities can lead to poor quality of life. COVID-19 also created a rapid increase in the obesity rates for children, the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) reports a pre-pandemic overweight/obesity rate of 25.1% among Hispanic children (Fryar et al., 2020). Throughout the years of the COVID-19 pandemic, there was a steady increase in the diagnosis of children with obesity or identified as overweight from 2020 to 2021, with a percentage of 32.8% to 50.7% respectively (Fryar et al., 2020).

Weight Management Electronic Applications

Despite the efforts to address obesity through traditional weight management strategies, the obesity rates continue to rise (Fryar et al., 2020; Ogden et al., 2018). Traditional weight management encompasses monitoring diet and exercise (Brown, 2011; Cardel & Taveras, 2020; Epstein et al., 1990; Franceschi et al., 2021). Traditional obesity management programs are

geared for adults, and little is changed within these programs when applied to children. Thus, the use of technology, which children have been exposed to throughout their lives, could affect weight management.

There are several electronic applications that can improve weight management in children (Al-Lami et al., 2020). There is an increased use of technology in the United States including its use in health care (Ratcliff et al., 2021). Patients are seeking health information on the web, interacting with providers over electronic mail and assessing their own health records via online electronic health record applications (Franceschi et al., 2021; Ratcliff et al., 2021). Technology use in healthcare presents with challenges and concerns. First, provider technology knowledge may be limited, and outpatient clinic implementation is difficult to track (Al-Lami et al., 2020; Cardel & Taveras, 2020). Second, the efficacy of the technology used is difficult to measure (Al-Lami et al., 2020; Cardel & Taveras, 2020). Lastly, the long-term effects of technology such as electronic applications for children are not fully understood (Al-Lami et al., 2020; Cardel & Taveras, 2020). Although many electronic applications have been developed to help with diet and exercise, researchers found that 66% of primary care providers were unaware of these electronic applications (Al-Lami et al., 2020; SanGiovanni et al., 2019). Researchers have developed a rating system to evaluate quality of existing weight management electronic applications to increase provider use (Al-Lami et al., 2020). Some researchers are concerned about long-term effects of electronic application use on children, and their associations with eating disorders (Cardel & Taveras, 2020).

Researchers have studied weight management with the use of electronic applications that track diet, and exercise (Choi et al., 2021; Cueto et al., 2019; Franceschi et al., 2021; Likhitweerawong et al., 2021; Rageliene et al., 2021). Some researchers studied the use of a

commercially developed electronic applications on children with obesity (Cueto et al., 2019; Likhitweerawong et al., 2021); while other researchers developed their own weight management electronic applications for the treatment of obesity in children (Choi et al., 2021; Franceschi et al., 2021; Rageliene et al., 2021). Researchers measured changes to a child's BMI, body weight, waist circumference, knowledge of nutrition and exercise, and quality of life. Researchers have found electronic applications to be effective in reducing BMI, body weight, and waist circumference (Choi et al., 2021; Cueto et al., 2019). Other researchers reported a decrease in weight loss but, no changes in BMI (Likhitweerawong et al., 2021). Researchers found that the use of electronic application increased knowledge of nutrition and exercise (Choi et al., 2021; Cueto et al., 2019; Franceschi et al., 2021; Likhitweerawong et al., 2021; Rageliene et al., 2021). Additionally, Likhitweerawong et al. (2021) found the use of electronic applications increased quality of life. Researchers have recognized limitations in their studies such as the need for a higher sample size and longer intervention implementation (Choi et al., 2021; Franceschi et al., 2021; Likhitweerawong et al., 2021; Rageliene et al., 2021).

The goal of this DNP project was to investigate the use of electronic application called SSMP among 10-to-12-year-old children diagnosed with obesity. Based on outcome measures identified in the literature review to identify effectiveness in decreasing childhood obesity and overweight, the PL choose outcome measures that included body weight, height, BMI, BMI%, waist circumference, self-esteem, and parent survey over 12 weeks. Furthermore, the study examined the effectiveness in helping children track their diet using the SSMP application.

Methods

The methods section discusses information about design, setting, participants, ethical considerations, procedures, and evaluation plan of this DNP project. The purpose of this DNP project was to investigate the effects of implementing an electronic application on obese school age children for weight management and to assess their change in self-esteem and parent survey. The SSMP weight management plan utilized the PDSA Quality Improvement (QI) model. The patients were followed at four, eight and 12 weeks and evaluated for changes to their body weight, waist circumference, BMI, and BMI%. In addition, the participant's self-esteem and parent survey were gathered at different intervals.

Design

This QI project utilized the PDSA model. The project goal was to establish a habit of tracking healthy eating among 10-12 years old school age children so they could manage their own weight. The DNP project measured participants' physiological characteristics (body weight, BMI, BMI%, waist circumference), the use of the SSMP, participants' self-esteem, and the participant parent survey to evaluate the effectiveness of the SSMP electronic application on weight management. The PDSA model, a robust and flexible model, was used as the framework for the project. The PDSA relies on expert knowledge from members of the organization who are aware of resources to address problems and has been used across multiple disciplines to improve quality of care (Institute for Hospital Improvement[IHI], 2022a; IHI, 2022b; Langley et al., 2009).

Sample/Participants

The PPC clinic served families from multiple cultural backgrounds, which included Hispanics, Blacks, non-Hispanic Whites, and Asians. The clinic served a wide spectrum of

pediatric patients, which included infants, school-age children, and adolescents. The population targeted for the DNP project were children 10-to-12-years-old and diagnosed with obesity. The age group was selected because the children were mature enough to understand “cause and effect” to lifestyle choices. Participants’ inclusion criteria for the project included a child who had a BMI of 95% or above, was 10-to-12 years old, had access to and operated one electronic device, and was a patient using the PPC clinic services. Participants were excluded if they were children with chronic illnesses to control for confounding variables that could affect the SSMP management project. The recruitment of families occurred from September 2022 and evaluated their interests in the project. The participation goal was to attain 25 children within the range of 10 to 12 years of age.

Ethical Considerations

The project leader (PL) received a letter supporting the implementation of this DNP project at the PPC clinic (Appendix E). The project was approved by the California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board (IRB) prior to commencing recruitment of participants for the project. Participants (children ages 10-12) and parents were given a written explanation of the project design, timeline, benefits and risks, and PL contact information.

The SSMP allowed all users to download and use mobile application without parental permission. The privacy policy was clearly stated in their mobile application, the USDA did not collect any personal identifiable information without the participant’s explicit consent. The privacy policy of the SSMP was transparent about the information collected, its use and how it was stored. The SSMP could gather and store information about browsing habits that improved the user experience while operating the mobile application. Additionally, the SSMP discussed the Children’s Online Privacy Protection Act (COPPA) that pertained to the collection of

electronic personal information from children under 13 years of age. The USDA complied with COPPA and re-iterated that they would not be collecting personal electronic information from the children.

The participant and parent data were de-identified and aggregated to protect their identity. The participants and their parents were informed that their participation was voluntary, and they had the right to discontinue their participation in the project at any time. Incentives were used to increase adherence to follow-up visits at four, eight, and 12 weeks. The incentives were of moderate cost, which consisted of a \$40 Target gift card.

Settings

The PPC clinic is a private practice clinic located in Southern California, and operated Monday through Friday from 8:30 AM to 5:00 PM. The clinic was owned by the attending physician and operated by the office manager. The clinic had one receptionist, one referral coordinator, and one medical assistant. There were three part-time Nurse Practitioners who practiced pediatric primary care on various days of the week. The office manager assisted with the resources needed for implementation of the DNP project such as directing office staff with scheduling appointments or triaging patients at the time of their visits. The office operated an electronic health record system named OfficeAlly, that was accessible to the PL. Patient data were gathered from OfficeAlly after IRB approval was obtained.

The PPC clinic served a majority of Medi-Cal insured children. The PPC clinic booked 25 patients per provider, per day and usually had 1-2 providers working each day. The receptionist confirmed well-child and physical exam appointments daily, verified insurance, and took messages for the office. The medical assistant took vitals on each patient and provided vaccinations. The medical assistant had additional duties such as providing laboratory orders,

giving nebulizer treatments, performing throat swabs, providing mental health resources, and collecting urine specimens. The office referral coordinator submitted referrals that were requested by providers and updated the patients on their referral status. The referral coordinator was a second medical assistant back up, who was called in when patient load was high. The office manager oversaw the daily operations of the clinic and provided the resources to the clinic. The attending physician conducted hospital rounds daily and provided care through a limited schedule at PPC clinic.

The PPC clinic utilized a traditional obesity management approach, which consisted of the provider counseling children with a BMI \geq 95%. The counseling consisted of the provider speaking with the patients about increasing their consumption of fruit and vegetables and incorporating active play. The provider then gathered information about body weight and BMI. The patient had a follow-up visit at one to three-months to determine the amount of body weight lost during that time.

Instruments/Measures

The DNP project investigated the effect of using SSMP, an electronic application, as a weight management tool among 10-to 12-year-old children diagnosed with obesity. SSMP weight management program monitored the use of the electronic application; the effects of tracking the children's healthy diet habits; and measured the effects on participant's body weight, BMI, BMI%, waist circumference, and self-esteem among 10 to 12 year olds. Additionally, the parent survey was developed to track daily intake servings of fruits, vegetables, cups of water, exercise minutes, and secondary measurement for the use SSMP application. SSMP is an electronic application developed by the USDA that incorporated ideologies spearheaded by Michelle Obama's campaign to create healthy habits in children (USDA, 2011).

The daily tracking of the participants' healthy diet was collected by the PL in two ways: 1) collected daily from text messages; 2) taken from the parent survey given during the in-person visits. The PL sent out a text message every evening at 7 PM to the parent or participant requesting the number of items tracked into the SSMP electronic application. The participant electronic application was deemed successful if the participants tracked at least 3 items into the application per day.

The participant's weight was measured using the Cardinal Detecto manual scale, which was collected by the PL at the time of their initial appointment. The participants were asked to wear lightweight clothing and remove their shoes before measuring and recording their body weight. The scale was calibrated prior to taking each weight measurement. The scale received yearly maintenance assuring reliability and accuracy of measurements.

The PL measured height using the Health-o-Meter® PORTROD Universal Wall Mounted Height Rod. The participants were asked to remove their shoes and push their heels and back against the wall and the Health-o-Meter to ensure proper height measuring. The height was recorded only at their first visit but used for the BMI calculation in every in-person visit. Waist circumference was measured by using a standard measuring tape in inches at the umbilicus by the PL. The measuring tape was placed flush to their skin at the umbilicus and then wrapped around the participant's waist.

BMI was calculated using the OfficeAlly health records system after input of the body weight and height results. The BMI is calculated by taking a person's height in inches and weight in pounds then, dividing the weight by the height squared (USPSTF, 2010). The BMI was then multiplied by 100, which provided the BMI percentage. Additionally, the BMI was double-

checked by the PL with the use of the CDC's BMI calculator, which required the participants' weight, height, sex, and age.

Self-esteem was measured using the Rosenberg scale (Appendix F). The scale was used without explicit permission, but the author's family requested that they be informed of its use. A letter was sent to the Morris Rosenberg Foundation care of the Department of Sociology at the University of Maryland explaining the DNP project and the use of the Rosenberg scale (Appendix F). The unidimensional self-esteem scale consisted of 10-questions that measured self-worth by investigating both positive and negative feelings of oneself (Rosenberg, 1965). Unidimensional design method was used to ensure that the investigation of one theme was captured within the questions on the scale (Ziegler & Hagemann, 1995). The scale measured responses on a 4-point Likert, ranging from 3, strongly agree to 0, strongly disagree. The scoring of the scale was achieved by adding together all the scaled scores for all questions to create a sum for the 10 items. The Rosenberg scale was validated and provided a scoring key to define the level of self-esteem: low self-esteem (0-10), moderate (11-26) and high self-esteem (27-30). The results and interpretation depended on the summation value of the scale; a high score indicated high self-esteem (Rosenberg, 1965).

The participant's parents were given the parent survey (Appendix G). The survey was developed by the PL and was used to measure the parent's observations of their child's weight management habits. The parent survey consisted of five questions evaluating the daily servings of fruits, vegetables, and water intake, minutes of exercise, and SSMP use. The survey reports were used to collect data at baseline, and at follow up visits of four, eight and 12 weeks.

Procedures

Parent and patients were recruited in September 2022 to evaluate interest in the project. The project was submitted for review and approval to the California State University, Long Beach IRB in July 2022. The estimated project start date was in September 2022, tentative to IRB approval (Appendix E). Parents who consented for their child to participate in the project had a scheduled appointment for a weight management visit. The parents were asked to bring their electronic device to the visit. The visits were scheduled and lasted approximately 20 minutes. Once the participant and parent checked-in for their visit each were given a printed survey to complete: children were given the Rosenberg self-esteem scale (Appendix F) and parents were given the Parent survey (Appendix G). The participant had their physiological variables (body weight, height, and waist circumference) measured by the PL. The BMI was calculated by the electronic medical records after the weight (pounds) and height (inches) were inputted in the system by the PL. Additionally, the PL checked the BMI measurements with the use of the CDC's BMI calculator to verify the accuracy. Once, the self-esteem survey, parent survey, and participants' measurements were completed, the PL met with the family in the exam room for MyPlate diet counseling and SSMP application set up.

Parents who consented for their child to participate in the project were guided by the PL to download the SSMP application to their electronic device. SSMP was an electronic application created with the USDA and was free of cost. The application provided two options for sign up, the user could register themselves or continue as a guest. The PL requested participants to register because registration allowed the users to track healthy diet intake of fruits, vegetables, grains, proteins, and dairy on multiple electronic devices. The login required an email and name. The parent's email was used and the name of their child. SSMP sent an email to

confirm and authorize the registration on the device. Once, the email registration was verified, the mobile system prompted the user to create a password. Their email address was also used to text daily messages to parents (Appendix H).

As a newly registered user, the SSMP application provided the user with two options for healthy diet tracking of nutrition groups. Option one, was when the SSMP software assigned the goals for daily intake of fruits, vegetables, grains, proteins, and dairy. Option two, the user defined their own goals of fruits, vegetables, grains, proteins, and dairy. The application had a MyPlate diet that was personalized to the patient's age and sex. The PL defined the diet goals for the school age child. The SSMP goals were defined at 1.5 cups of fruits, 2.5 cups of vegetables, 6 ounces of grains, 5 ounces of low-fat protein, and 3 servings of low-fat dairy per day (see Appendix I). SSMP offered notifications at different time intervals as a reminder to the user to track their intake of fruits, vegetables, grains, proteins, and dairy. The SSMP application offered optional quizzes to motivate and evaluate the progress of the preset nutrition group goals. The application did not track or collect personal information such as age, or weight. The application was free of cost and did not require a credit card in order to sign up.

The PL demonstrated how to navigate through the SSMP electronic application. The child participants were instructed to use SSMP daily to track their intake of fruits, vegetables, grains, proteins, and dairy. The MyPlate diet counseling was extensive, the PL provided handouts to the family to reinforce the nutritional requirements at home (Appendix I). The participants were told about appropriate servings sizes of each daily nutritional requirement (fruits, vegetables, proteins, grains, dairy, and water intake). The PL discussed the vitamins and minerals associated with consuming each food group. The families were encouraged to ask

dietary questions. Participants were asked to follow up every 4 weeks in-person to collect physiological variables, self-esteem survey, and parent survey.

In addition to the SSMP application, parents who consented to enroll their children received two text message reminders per day. The first text message was sent in the morning and provided a tip about exercise (Appendix H). The second daily text message was sent in the evening inquiring about how many items were tracked in the SSMP application for the day. The PL defined application use if the patient tracked 3 or more items in the application daily. The usage of the SSMP application was assessed daily from the responses to the evening text from parents or participant. The PL used a text message program called Mighty Text, the program allowed the PL to individually send out text messages to each participant or as a group. The Mighty Text program had other advantages such as pre-scheduling texts.

In addition, optional ongoing diet and exercise counseling was provided to those who agreed to attend the weekly support meetings from the PL. The support meetings were additional counseling provided at no cost to the participants every Thursday from 4 PM to 5 PM over Zoom, which is an online communication platform. Multiple topics were discussed, such as healthy meals, nutrition groups and their benefits, junk food, reading food labels, demonstration of healthy and quick breakfast, coping during holidays, benefits of sleep, and basic caloric demands of the body. The weekly support meeting aimed to provide the participants with additional support in nutrition and exercise to help them retain nutrition knowledge. The meetings were not recorded, and no patient information was collected during meetings. The DNP project timeline and measurement table are illustrated in Appendices J and K, respectively.

Data Analysis

The evaluation phase consisted of analyzing the gathered data using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics were useful in evaluating participant characteristics (age, gender and racial background) with the use of tracking the frequencies, percentages, averages, and standard deviations. Inferential statistics such as the paired sample t-test was useful in comparing the means, to further investigate a significant change in the dependent variables (participants' body weight, BMI, BMI%, waist circumference, self-esteem score and SSMP use) after the intervention (Wadhwa & Marappa-Ganeshan, 2022). The paired sample t-test evaluated the measured variables (body weight, BMI, BMI%, waist circumference, self-esteem score, and SSMP application use) after introducing the SSMP weight management plan at a p-value of .05.

All the numerical values were entered into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet without identifying information related to the participant and their parent. The data was stored on the PL's office computer that was password protected.

Results

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the SSMP weight management project data. The descriptive statistics were used to evaluate the participants' physiological characteristics (body weight, waist circumference, BMI, BMI%, the use of the SSMP electronic application, participants' self-esteem, and the participants' parent's survey (Table 2-9 in Appendix L). Inferential statistics were used to compare the effects of SSMP weight management interventions using the paired sample t-test.

Sample Demographic Characteristics

The SSMP weight management project started with 18 participants; only 14 completed the 12-week project with an attrition rate of 22%. The average age of the participants was 10.8 years, with SD of 0.89. The sample included eight males (57.1%) and six females (42.9%). Participants' racial background was predominantly Hispanic (n=12, 85.8%), with one participant with a Samoa (7.1%) background and one participant identified as White/Hispanic (7.1%) descent. All participants were in the 5th or 6th grade.

Sample Physiological Characteristics

The participants' physiological variables measured were body weight, waist circumference, BMI, and BMI% (Table 2-5 in Appendix L). The average pre-intervention body weight was 138 pounds with SD of 28, and post-intervention weight was 142 pounds with SD of 31. Counter to expectations, the participants' average body weight increased after the implementation of the SSMP weight management project. The paired t-test showed a significant increase in the participant's body weight with t value of 2.16 and p-value of .015. The average pre-intervention waist circumference decreased from an average of 36 inches with SD of 4 to 34

inches with SD of 4. The paired sample t-test resulted in a significant decrease in waist circumference at a t value of 2.16 and p-value of less than .001.

The average pre-intervention BMI (M=27.98, SD=3.79) was lower than the post-intervention score (M=28.71, SD=4.27). The paired sample t-test confirmed a significant increase in BMI post-intervention with a $t(13) = 2.16$ and $p = 0.011$. The average BMI% remained stable during the pre-participation (M=98.07%, SD=1.14) and the post-participation (M=98.00%, SD=1.52). The paired t-test did not show a significant change, with a t-value of 2.16 and a p-value of .72.

SSMP Application Use

The use of the SSMP electronic application was tracked in two ways. The PL sent a daily evening text message requesting the participant to provide the number of tracked items listed in their SSMP application. Tracked items were fruit, vegetables, grains, proteins, and dairy. Some participants self-reported the number of tracked items, while others responded via their parental unit. Some parents had safety concerns with the use of electronics and required their children to communicate with the PL via their electronic devices. Both the self-report and parent responses were collected by the PL and logged into a spreadsheet in Microsoft excel over the 12-week duration. Only 57% (n=8) of participants responded to the evening text sent by the PL requesting the daily number of tracked items into the SSMP application.

There were incentives provided after each in-person visit to motivate participants to continue with the SSMP diet, tracking with the SSMP application, and follow-up. After the 4-week in-person visit (visit #1), the PL introduced an additional drawing that would be exclusive to the participants that responded to the evening text. The drawing improved the participants' response to the evening text by 25% (n=2).

Self-Esteem

The participants' self-esteem was measured by using a modified Rosenberg scale. The average pre-participation self-esteem score was noted to be at a moderate level with a score of 19.57 and SD of 4.83, and a post-participation self-esteem score that dropped but remained at a moderate level of 18.86 with SD of 6.92. The sample t-test did not confirm a significant change in the participant's self-esteem ($t(13) = 2.16$ and $p = .633$).

Parent Survey

The parent survey (Appendix G) was used to measure the participants' daily nutrition intake, minutes of exercise and a second modality to measure the participants' tracking of nutrition with the use of the SSMP electronic application during the in-person visits (0-, 8- and 12-weeks). Participants' nutritional intake was also collected through the paper-pencil parent survey in which parents were asked to provide information regarding their children's daily servings of fruits (a serving=1/2 cup), vegetables (a servings=1/2 cup), and water intake (a serving=8 ounces). The parent survey responses ranged from 0, 1-2, 3-4, 5-6, 7-8 servings of fruits and vegetables; and ranged from 0-1, 2-3, 4-5, 6-7, 8 or more cups of water per day.

Participants' intake of fruit, vegetable, and water improved from pre- to post-intervention (Table 7 in Appendix L). At baseline, 71% ($n=10$) of participants consumed a single fruit serving per day, and 64% ($n=9$) of participants consumed one vegetable serving per day. At post-intervention, 50% ($n=7$) participants consumed 3-4 servings of fruits, and 50% ($n=7$) consumed three servings of vegetables per day. Water intake was evenly distributed among participants at the baseline visits (21% drinking 2 cups, 36% drinking 4 cups, 21% drinking 6 cups, and 21% drinking 8 cups of water daily). Participants' post-intervention water intake results were 94% ($n=13$), drinking 4-8 cups of water per day at 12-weeks.

The minutes of daily exercise were measured by the parent survey at the initial, 8-week, and 12-week in-person visits. Parents of participants were allowed to select from ranges of 0, 10-15, 20-30, 31-40, and 45 minutes and above of exercise per day. The majority of participant (n=10, 71%) reported exercising 10-30 minutes per day. In the post-intervention, the majority of participants (n=8, 57%) reported exercising 31-45 minutes

The parents of participants were surveyed on the number of daily tracked items they logged into the SSMP application at 8-weeks and 12-weeks. The range for the tracked items included 0-1, 2-3, 4-5, 6-7, or 8 or more per day. Most participants (n=10, 71%) reported tracking 4 items of less into the SSMP. In the post-intervention, participants (n=8, 57%) tracked 4 or more items into the SSMP application (Table 9 in Appendix L).

Additional Findings

Over the 12-week project, there were comments and concerns made by participants and their families to the PL. Several participants and parents stated that the SSMP weight management project improved the intake of fruits and vegetables. Five out of the 14 participants admitted the weekly support meeting increased their nutritional knowledge. Two of the five participants that attended meetings, admitted that SSMP application kept them accountable of their nutritional goals. One out of five participants who attended meetings admitted the SSMP weight management project prompted increased consumption of new foods.

Two participants reported they were more interested in eating home cooked foods over fast food. One parent and participant dyad stated that the weekly support classes helped them identify unhealthy and healthy foods and reinforced the SSMP nutritional requirements. In addition, the parent was surprised to see her child inquire about which vegetable was being served for dinner. One participant reported enjoying the optional supportive meetings that

occurred once a week in which healthy breakfast options were discussed and being able to ask about additional healthy recipes during those meetings.

Numerous participants expressed that the SSMP weight management project allowed them to be more consistent with exercise. One participant said they chose to be active during recess and lunch daily. Another participant stated that he started to train for basketball tryouts.

During the third week of the project, a parent reached out to the PL regarding her concern about her participant's level of engagement with the SSMP weight management project. She stated that her participant had increased their daily caloric intake because of the SSMP nutrition requirements. The parent reported that the participant would forget to follow the nutritional recommendations for the intake of fruits and vegetables during the day, and prior to bedtime, the participant would force-feed himself some fruit to meet the daily requirement of the SSMP. In another situation, the participant was reported to have taken a 3-week vacation to El Salvador to visit grandparents during the project.

Discussion

The SSMP weight management project was performed in a PPC clinic. The aim of the project was to assess the effects of implementing an electronic application on school age children for weight management. This section discusses the results from the project including participant physiological characteristics, self-esteem, nutrition, exercise, and electronic application use.

Physiological Characteristics

Body Weight, BMI, and BMI Percentage

The post-intervention participants' body weight, BMI, and BMI% results were surprising since it was inconsistent with the expectations. Participants' average body weight increased significantly from the pre-intervention to the post-intervention measurements ($p=.015$).

Similarly, participants' BMI increased significantly ($p=0.011$), however, the BMI% remained stable after the intervention. Although, BMI is widely used to measure obesity worldwide, it does not differentiate between muscular or fat weight changes in children overtime (Freedman et al., 2022). Researchers have suggested that BMI lacks heterogeneity in diagnosing children from different races and gender (Javed et al., 2014). The SSMP weight management findings may have been influenced by environmental factors such as social, economic, and family units.

Social Factors. The project timeline was set from September 2022 to December of 2022, the timeline included major holidays (Halloween, Thanksgiving, and Christmas), which may have affected participants' body weight. Fahey et al. (2019) studied the impact of U.S. holidays on adults' weight over a 12-month weight loss study; they learned that participants gained weight more rapidly during November to January. The months of October, November, and December include major holidays; therefore, it is possible that the children celebrated with family and consumed foods with high-caloric content that led to an increase of body weight and BMI.

The nutritional requirements for the SSMP are based on FDA's dietary guidelines, they were developed to meet nutrition needs and prevent chronic disease (Tapsell et al., 2016). The nutritional guidelines can improve feelings of satiety. On the other hand, inappropriate dietary habits such as intake of high sodium, simple carbohydrates, and low amount of water have been associated with an increase of the consumption of food (Amin & Mercer, 2016). As discussed in the results, some participants had difficulty transitioning to the MyPlate diet, which may have led to the increase in participant body weight and BMI.

In addition, the ending of daylight savings, which started in November 6, 2022, resulted in less daylight during the evenings, which may limit outdoor playtime. Goodman et al. (2014) reviewed a pool of accelerometer data collected from children ages 5-16 from nine different countries, and they observed that longer daylight in the evenings resulted in higher physical activity.

Economic Factors. According to Pereira and Olivera (2020), 49 million people entered poverty in 2020 globally, causing families to experience poverty or financial insecurity. Many families were affected financially by the COVID-19 pandemic, as many parents could not work or lost their jobs. Fresh fruits and vegetables are more costly than packaged and canned foods. The economic changes in the families have led to changes in the staple items in the home. Chang et al. (2021) found that COVID pandemic caused significant changes to children's diet habits; children have increased consumption of foods that contain shelf-life such as sweetened beverages, potato chips, and sweets. In the clinic, parents admitted to buying their children chips, dehydrated soups, or fast foods because they knew their children would eat them. Parents have admitted that having their children eat a full meal gives them peace of mind.

Family Factors. Family household units can be defined as single parents, grandparents as caregivers, dual partners, and can be accompanied with or without siblings. These family units may have vast differences in nutrition intake. Fowler et al. (2020) found that parent-child dyads that were enrolled in family-based weight loss treatment were more effective in making diet and lifestyle changes that led to weight loss. A child that may be left in afterschool programs may get more exercise and have more nutritional options, while a child that is left alone after school may eat whatever is in the household.

Waist Circumference

The participants' average waist circumference decreased over the 12-week project implementation; the change was significant. Many participants expressed that the SSMP weight management project allowed them to be more consistent with engaging in physical activity. The SSMP participants reported increased active play during school hours and trying new organized sports. The waist circumference is associated with visceral fat; therefore, participants have decreased their visceral fat over the course of the project. The waist circumference reduction and body weight increase may indicate that the participants were losing fat and gaining muscle. Khanna et al. (2022) studied the validity of BMI and waist circumference as early predictors of chronic disease; they found a positive correlation between BMI and waist circumference. The opposite effect was observed in the SSMP weight management project, likely resulting from the short project timeline.

Self-Esteem

The Rosenberg scale was used to measure the participant's self-esteem, which remained in the moderate range, indicating that the project did not improve the participant's self-esteem. The SSMP weight management project introduced an electronic application to empower

participants to track their nutrition goals. Additionally, weekly meetings were provided over Zoom platform to provide continual education and provide a platform of discussion. These interventions were expected to increase participant self-esteem from the pre-intervention measurement to the post-intervention measurement. Self-esteem may not have changed since many of the participants had an increase in body weight, which led them to perceive it negatively. Additionally, the length of the project may not have been long enough to be able to measure changes in self-esteem since this trait may require long term intervention to affect it.

Nutrition

The continuous dietary support has been shown to improve eating habits and reduce BMI (Henderson, 2021). The weight management support can be delivered by electronic application notification, text messages, virtual meetings, or clinic visits. The SSMP participants' parents reported an increase in consumption of daily servings of fruits, vegetables, and water in their child post-intervention. In addition, the SSMP participants expressed that the virtual weekly support meeting prompted increase consumption of new foods.

Exercise

The participants' exercise collected by parent survey showed a daily increase in minutes after the intervention. The daily motivational texting included a video or exercise tip to stay active in and outdoors (Appendix H). Texting has been proven to be a motivator among children to increase their intake of fruits and vegetables (Al-Lami et al., 2020; Henderson, 2021; Rageliene et al., 2021). In this project, it seems that the morning text messages increased daily exercise by motivating participants to get active.

Electronic Application Use

The lack of tracking into the SSMP electronic application from participants may be due to their inability to have the electronic application on their own device. Many of the participants did not have their own phones or preferred to communicate through their parent's electronic devices. This meant that many parents received their child's daily text message alert, and it was difficult to determine if the child ever received the information. Participants may have also experienced notification fatigue and thus ignored the daily text messages. Smartphones have multiple applications with notifications, so the participants may have become fatigued and neglected to respond to the evening text message.

Recommendations

The SSMP weight management project used different forms of informatics (electronic application, texting, and virtual platform) to treat obesity in children. The project resulted in low number of participants using the SSMP electronic application consistently, possibly due to problems with navigating within the application. Although, the participants and their families received support with downloading the SSMP application. Once, the application was downloaded, the project leader (PL) navigated through the SSMP to show the participant how to use the tracking application during this initial visit. Despite the training, many participants did not consistently use the SSMP to track their intake of food. The PL did not evaluate participants' knowledge on SSMP application navigation, which may have helped to explain why the participants did not track their food intake. Their lack of consistent use of the SSMP may have been due to a knowledge gap in application use. Future projects should include a return-demonstration of the SSMP application by participants and or parents to reinforce the navigation skills taught during the initial training.

The virtual weekly support meeting had low participation. These meetings were non mandatory and were made optional for participants with the intention of reducing the stress associated with participation in the project. Participants all were engaged in different levels of academic or extracurricular activities, and their parents had different work schedules, which made it difficult to participate in the weekly meetings. A future recommendation would be to provide the SSMP weight management nutritional meetings at two different times a week, since many of the parents reported that they were unable to attend the weekly meeting due to scheduling conflicts. By providing two opportunities a week, this may increase participation in the nutritional meetings. Multiple participants and parents who attended the nutritional meetings improved their nutritional knowledge, which improved their eating habits.

The SSMP weight management project measured obesity using multiple measures (body weight, BMI, BMI%, and waist circumference). Given that participant weight and BMI increased, with no change in BMI% and a decrease in waist circumference, the measurement of different body areas such as the arms and legs, could have demonstrated to the participants that they were losing inches in other parts of their bodies. The additional measurements can provide validation for the participants that focused on body weight as a measure of their success.

Implications

The SSMP weight management project contributed to understanding the effects of electronic tracking on weight management in primary care. Current research, states that the increase consumption of fruits and vegetables in children may promote healthier eating habits leading to a decrease in obesity rates in children. Despite, the increases in participant consumption of daily servings of fruits, vegetables and water, the results need to be validated by further research. Future research can identify if the changes were a result of the electronic

application or merely the attention paid to the eating habits of the participants. The effects of the electronic application use can be powerful in restructuring weight management programs for children in primary care. Current clinical practices for obesity management are to educate families about improving diet and increasing exercise, then to follow up in 2-3 months to measure their weight. At the follow-up visit, the provider may refer a patient to a dietician for further dietary support.

The SSMP weight management project is a feasible intervention in primary care and a cost-effective plan to support patients. Primary care providers are at an advantage in impacting obesity rates in children because they have established rapport with their patients.

Limitations

The SSMP weight management project was 12-weeks long, which may not have been long enough to evaluate if the use of the application affected BMI. Research indicates that BMI and waist circumference are positively correlated at 24 months and studies that took place over 5 years (Khanna et al., 2022). Thus, the limited project timeline did not allow for the measurement of the effect of the SSMP weight management intervention on the participants.

The participants' BMI was calculated by taking the participants body weight and divided by their height squared. The body weight was measured at each in-person visit but height was only measured once at the start of the project. Participants were 10 -12 years olds and could have had a height growth spurt due to the onset of puberty that would impact the BMI calculation (Giglione et al., 2021).

The project participants were mostly from a Hispanic background, limiting the SSMP weight management intervention results to one ethnicity. The sample size was small, which limited the amount of data gathered for the analysis. Smaller sample sizes make it difficult to

generalize the findings and determine the influence of the intervention on creating behavior changes. In another situation, the participant was reported to have taken a 3-week vacation to El Salvador to visit grandparents during the project. This limited the PL's ability to track his use of SSMP during those three weeks.

During the project implementation, there was a malfunction in the text messaging component of the SSMP program used by the PL to send out daily text messages. The result was that participants received duplicate evening text messages that the families felt were too frequent. The PL investigated the cause for these duplicate text messages and resolved the issue.

The PL collected physiological data during the in-person meeting, which took place every four weeks. The parent survey was collected at baseline and subsequently at 8 and 12 weeks from the start of the project. The parent survey was not collected at week 4 of the project. This was due to a late decision to increase the number of parent surveys collected. The parent surveys were then collected in weeks 8 and 12.

The SSMP weight management project was designed using the PDSA cycle to optimize the project. The inability to run another PDSA cycle hampered the PL's ability to address problems within the project, such as measuring other parts of the body that may be more prone to weight loss. More supportive nutritional meetings should be held to help increase the discussion about healthy eating.

Conclusion

Implementation of the SSMP weight management project affected the participants' physiological variables. More specifically, participants' body weight and BMI increased but waist circumference decreased, indicating that they lost body fat and increased their muscle mass. Secondly, the project increased participants' consumption of fruits, vegetables, and water

intake and increased their overall exercise measured in minutes. Utilizing an electronic application, providing weekly support and daily motivational text messages may be a feasible and effective weight management approach for children with obesity in primary care.

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Appendix A

The PDSA Model

Figure 1

The PDSA Model

Note. PDSA model (IHI, 2022a; IHI, 2022b)

Appendix B

Information-Motivation-Behavioral Model Conceptual Framework

Figure 2

Integration of the IMB Model into the Plan phase of the PDSA cycle

Note. Information-Motivation-Behavioral Model (Fisher et al., 2003)

Appendix C
Fishbone Diagram

Figure 3

Fishbone diagram identifying variables contributing to obesity and self-esteem

Note. Fishbone diagram

Appendix D

Pediatric Primary Care Clinic Obesity Run Charts

Figure 4

Obesity Follow-up Visits in 2018

Note. Obesity follow-up visits in 2018 for primary pediatric care clinic.

Figure 5

Obesity Follow-up Visits in 2019

Note. Obesity follow-up visits in 2019 for primary pediatric care clinic.

Figure 6*Obesity Follow-up Visits in 2020*

Note. Obesity follow-up visits in 2020 for primary pediatric care clinic. A break in data point due to problems with the electronic health system. COVID-19 pandemic “stay at home” mandate occurred in March 2020.

Figure 7

Obesity Follow-up Visits in 2021

Note. Obesity follow-up visits in 2021 for primary pediatric care clinic. COVID-19 pandemic precautions ongoing from March 2020

Appendix E

Letters of Approval

Pediatric Primary Care Clinic Approval

Pediatrics

Institutional Approval Letter

June 7, 2022

This letter is to show that, I, Dr. [REDACTED] M.D., as the owner and attending physician of Blanca Hampton, M.D. Clinic, give permission to [REDACTED] to conduct the project titled "The Impact of Using an Electronic Application on Weight Management for School-Age Children with Obesity in a Pediatric Primary Care Clinic: A Quality Improvement Project" on the following unit(s) Dr. [REDACTED] Outpatient Clinic.

Upon obtaining all necessary clearances from the Attending Physician and office management at the clinic, and after obtaining the necessary IRB determination/approval, the above-named project lead is allowed to:

- (1) Collect data (age, sex, weight, height, body mass index, waist circumference, psychometric scale, parental perception survey)
- (2) Access necessary documents/data (electronic medical records and contact information)
- (3) Conduct necessary interactions with staff/patients relevant to their project (office receptionist, medical assistance, patient and families consenting to research study)
- (4) Utilize office exam room, office telephone, and office printer to collect pre-and post-survey

The project lead is responsible for ensuring that all activities related to conducting the project are in compliance with the policies that govern practice, HIPPA, and research and research-related regulations at Dr. Hampton's Clinic and its covered entities.

If you have any questions or concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Signature: [REDACTED]

Signature: [REDACTED]

Name: [REDACTED] M.D.

Name: [REDACTED]

Title: M.D. / Owner

Title: *Certified Pediatric Nurse Practitioner*

Contact Information: [REDACTED]

Contact Information: [REDACTED]

Institutional Review Board Approval

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LONG BEACH

OFFICE OF RESEARCH & SPONSORED PROGRAMS

DATE: September 7, 2022

TO: Maydole Aldalur, cDNP, MSN, BSN
FROM: California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board

PROJECT TITLE: [1924450-3] Using an Electronic Application on Weight Management for School-Age Children with Obesity in a Pediatric Primary Care Clinic: A Quality Improvement Project

REFERENCE #: 22-262
SUBMISSION TYPE: Amendment/Modification

on REVIEW TYPE: Administrative Review

ACTION: APPROVED
APPROVAL DATE: September 6, 2022
EXPIRATION DATE: July 26, 2023

This is to advise you that the Institutional Review Board for the Protection of Human Subjects (IRB) of California State University, Long Beach, has reviewed your protocol application.

Approval is conditional upon your willingness to carry out your continuing responsibilities under University policy. This project must adhere to the following conditions:

1. You must clearly indicate in the header or footer of each page of your approved Informed Consent Form and recruitment material as follows: **"Approved from September 6, 2022 to July 26, 2023 by the CSULB IRB."**
2. **If you need to make changes/revision to this approved project, you must submit a Request for Amendment to an Approved Protocol in addition to any documents affected by the requested change. Submit these documents as a subsequent package to this approved project via IRBNet. You are not allowed to implement any changes to your research activities prior to obtaining final approval of you**

requested amendment from the CSULB IRB.

3. You are required to inform the Director of Research Integrity and Compliance, Office of Research & Sponsored Programs, via email at ORSPCompliance@csulb.edu within twenty-four hours of any adverse event in the conduct of research involving human subjects. The report shall include the nature of the adverse event, the names of the persons affected, the extent of the injury or breach of confidentiality or data security, if any, and any other information material to the situation.
4. Maintain your research records as detailed in the protocol.
5. If you would like to continue this research after this one-year period, please submit an Annual Check-in Form, and when applicable, updated IRB Application and all relevant project documents to the CSULB IRB one month prior to your project expiration date of July 26, 2023.

Should you have any questions about the conduct of your research under this protocol, particularly about providing informed consent and unexpected contingencies, please do not hesitate to contact the IRB Office via email, IRB@csulb.edu, or call (562) 985-8147. Please specify your project title and reference number in all correspondence with this committee. We wish you the best of success in your research.

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board's records.

1250 Bellflower Blvd., Long Beach, CA 90840
Ph. (562) 985-8147 Fax. (562) 985-8665

Appendix F

Self Esteem Scale

Rosenberg Scale (modified)

Directions:

Please read the following statements and choose the best answer for you.

	Very True	True	Not True	Definitely Not True
I am happy with myself				
Sometimes I think I'm no good at all				
There are lots of good things about me				
I can do things as well as most other children				
I don't have much to be proud of				
I feel useless at times				
I feel that I'm as good as everyone else				
I wish I cared about myself more				
I often feel like a failure				
I feel good about myself				

Adapted from Rosenberg (1965).

Rosenberg Self-esteem Scale Approval

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Rosenberg Self Esteem Scale

The Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale is perhaps the most widely-used self-esteem measure in social science research. Dr. Rosenberg was a Professor of Sociology at the University of Maryland from 1975 until his death in 1992. He received his Ph.D. from Columbia University in 1953, and held a variety of positions, including at Cornell University and the National Institute of Mental Health, prior to coming to Maryland. Dr. Rosenberg is the author or editor of numerous books and articles, and his work on the self-concept, particularly the dimension of self-esteem, is world-renowned.

The Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale is now in the public domain, meaning you may use it without charge and without notifying the Sociology Department. This permission extends to making translations or adaptations as you see fit, consistent with traditional scholarly attribution practices. The department does not maintain any information on the scale beyond what is linked below, and cannot advise on its use.

[Self Esteem: What Is it?](#)

[Rosenberg Scale FAQ](#)

[Using the Self Esteem Scale](#)

Last modified: 03/02/2022 - 11:29 am

Letter Requesting Approval from Morris Rosenberg Foundation

**MAYDOLE
ALDALUR**

Certified Pediatric Nurse Practitioner-PC, Doctoral candidate

CONTACT

PHONE:
[REDACTED]

EMAIL:
[REDACTED]

The Morris Rosenberg Foundation
c/o Department of Sociology
University of Maryland
2112 Art/Soc Building
College Park, MD 20742-1315

Dear Sir/Madam:

I am a doctoral student from California State University Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) Consortium writing my DNP project, under the direction of my DNP advisors Dr. Jadalla and Dr. Khalil.

I would like your permission to use the Rosenberg self-esteem scale in my DNP project. The purpose of my project is to use an electronic application among children aged 10-12 with a diagnosis of obesity and examine the outcome on weight management and self-esteem.

I would like to use and print your survey under the following conditions:

- I will use the surveys only for my research study and will not sell or use it with any compensated or curriculum development activities.
- At your request, I will send a copy of my completed DNP project to your attention upon completion of the study.

If these are acceptable terms and conditions, please indicate so by replying to me through e-mail:
[REDACTED]

Sincerely,

Doctoral Candidate

Maydole Aldalur

Appendix G
Parent Survey

Parent Survey

1. How many fresh fruit servings does your child take per day? (1 serving = 1/2 c or small fruit)
No fruits 1-2 3-4 5-6 7-8
2. How many vegetable servings does your child take per day? (1 serving = 1/2 c or small fruit)
No vegetables 1-2 3-4 5-6 7-8
3. How much water does your child take per day? (1 serving = 1 cup = 8 ounces)
0-1 2-3 4-5 6-7 8 or more
4. How many minutes of active play or exercise does your child complete per day?
0 10-15 min 20-30 min 31-40 min 45 min or more
5. How many times per day did your child log any of the items (food, exercise, or beverages) into the SSMP electronic application?
0-1 2-3 4-5 6-7 8 or more

Appendix H

Motivation Text Messages

Daily Exercise Text Messages

1. Visit the park
2. Jumping jack challenge
3. Race
4. Obstacle course
5. Yoga
6. Dance party
7. Walk outside
8. Ride your bike
9. Ride your scooter
10. Basketball
11. Soccer
12. Swim
13. Skip jump rope
14. Hide and seek game
15. Play catch
16. Play football
17. Crab walk race
18. Hula hoop
19. Potato sack race
20. Animal walks
21. Volleyball
22. Zumba for Kids
23. Hike with family

Appendix I

My Plate Diet Handouts

Handout 1

Start simple with MyPlate Plan

The benefits of healthy eating add up over time, bite by bite. Small changes matter. Start Simple with MyPlate.

A healthy eating routine is important at every stage of life and can have positive effects that add up over time. It's important to eat a variety of fruits, vegetables, grains, protein foods, and dairy or fortified soy alternatives. When deciding what to eat or drink, choose options that are full of nutrients. Make every bite count.

Food Group Amounts for 1,800 Calories a Day for Ages 9 to 13 Years

<p>Dairy</p>				
<p>1½ cups</p>	<p>2½ cups</p>	<p>6 ounces</p>	<p>5 ounces</p>	<p>3 cups</p>
<p>Focus on whole fruits</p> <p>Focus on whole fruits that are fresh, frozen, canned, or dried.</p>	<p>Vary your veggies</p> <p>Choose a variety of colorful fresh, frozen, and canned vegetables—make sure to include dark green, red, and orange choices.</p>	<p>Make half your grains whole grains</p> <p>Find whole-grain foods by reading the Nutrition Facts label and ingredients list.</p>	<p>Vary your protein routine</p> <p>Mix up your protein foods to include seafood; beans, peas, and lentils; unsalted nuts and seeds; soy products; eggs; and lean meats and poultry.</p>	<p>Move to low-fat or fat-free dairy milk or yogurt (or lactose-free dairy or fortified soy versions)</p> <p>Look for ways to include dairy or fortified soy alternatives at meals and snacks throughout the day.</p>
<p>Activity</p>	<p>Be active your way:</p> <p>Children 6 to 17 years old should move at least 60 minutes every day.</p>			

Handout 2

Small Changes Matter.

Start Simple With MyPlate Today.

Healthy eating is important at every stage of life.

Handout 3

Choose from these simple tips to help you...

Focus on whole fruits

- Start your day with **fruit at breakfast**. Top cereal with your favorite seasonal fruit, add bananas or chopped apples to pancakes, or mix a spoonful or two of raisins into hot oatmeal.
- Keep **ready-to-eat fruits** in the refrigerator for a quick snack.
- For dinner, chop up a combination of seasonal, frozen, or canned fruits to make a **quick fruit salsa** to top fish or chicken. Add fruit such as orange sections, apple wedges, or grapes to a **salad**.

Vary your veggies

- Add shredded carrots to the lettuce and tomato **in your sandwich**, make **soup** from the veggies in your vegetable drawer, and **snack on raw vegetables**.
- Try a **stir-fry** with fresh or frozen vegetables for a quick meal or easy side dish.
- Pick out a vegetable that the family has not tried and **get a new recipe** from a cookbook, website, supermarket, or friend.

Make half your grains whole grains

- For breakfast, enjoy a whole-grain-based **hot or cold cereal**. Consider trying whole-grain puffs or flakes that are new to you—you might discover a new favorite!
- Instead of sandwich bread, try a **whole-grain pita, tortillas, naan or other whole-grain flatbread, sliced breads, or rolls**.
- Create your own trail mix with whole-grain cereal or enjoy whole-grain crackers with turkey, hummus, or avocado for a **healthy whole-grain snack**.

Handout 3 continued

Protein

Vary your protein routine

- **Broil lean beef cuts** like sirloin, top round, or flank steak. **Roast lean types of pork tenderloin or loin chops** and slice into strips for dinner, salads, and sandwiches.
- **Have fish or seafood twice a week.** Make a lunchtime sandwich or salad with canned tuna, grill fresh or frozen tilapia or salmon for dinner, or enjoy fish tacos.
- **Meatless meals** are tasty and budget friendly. Try bean-based vegetarian chili or lentil soup, grilled or braised tofu with vegetables, or adding nuts to salads.

Dairy

Move to low-fat or fat-free dairy milk or yogurt (or lactose-free dairy or fortified soy versions)

- **Add low-fat or fat-free dairy** to oatmeal or pureed vegetable soups instead of water, and to smoothies or scrambled eggs.
- The nutrients in dairy are **important at every stage of life.** Include foods like low-fat or fat-free dairy milk or yogurt. Need an alternative? Try lactose-free dairy milk or yogurt that's low-fat or fat-free or fortified soy versions.
- Looking for a beverage? Grab a **glass of low-fat or fat-free milk or fortified soy milk** (soy beverage). Choose the unsweetened option.

Choose foods and beverages with less added sugars, saturated fat, and sodium

Limit

Tips for Less Added Sugars

- Choose **packaged foods that have less or no added sugars**, such as canned fruit packed in 100% juice for an easy snack, plain yogurt (you can add your own fruit), and unsweetened applesauce.
- Try chilled, **plain water or sparkling water with a squeeze of fruit** for a splash of flavor. Limit sugary beverages such as soda, lemonade, sports drinks, or fruit drinks.

Tips for Less Saturated Fat

- In place of foods higher in saturated fat, **look for foods like nuts, seeds, and fatty fish** like tuna, salmon, trout, and mackerel, which are high in unsaturated fats and a healthier choice.
- Choose **canola oil, olive oil, or other vegetable oils** for cooking.

Tips for Less Salt and Sodium

- Start simple by choosing foods with less sodium. **Check the Nutrition Facts label and choose foods with a lower percent (%) Daily Value (DV) for sodium** on the label, especially if a family member has high blood pressure, diabetes, or kidney disease.
- **Cook at home!** Preparing your own food puts you in control of how much sodium goes into your meals. Add flavor to foods with herbs, spices, lemon, lime, and vinegar instead of salt or seasonings high in sodium.

Handout 4

Start *simple*
with **MyPlate**

Healthy Eating for Kids

Healthy eating is important at every age. Offer kids a variety of fruits, vegetables, grains, protein foods, and dairy or fortified soy alternatives. When deciding on foods and beverages, choose options that are full of nutrients and limited in added sugars, saturated fat, and sodium. Start with these tips:

Offer variety

Include choices from each food group—fruits, vegetables, grains, protein foods, and dairy or fortified soy alternatives—in meals and snacks during each day.

Connect at mealtime

Eat meals together whenever possible. Turn off the TV and put away phones and tablets, so you can “unplug” and focus on healthy foods and each other.

Make good nutrition easy

Designate a shelf or a drawer in your fridge for your kids. Stock it with cut-up fruits and vegetables, yogurt, nut butters, and whole-wheat mini bagels and crackers.

Think about their drinks

Make water and low-fat or fat-free dairy milk or fortified soy alternatives easy options to grab in your home. Have ready-to-go containers filled and in the fridge to take on outings.

Get kids involved

Depending on their age, kids can peel fruits, assemble salads, measure, scoop, and slice. Let them create and name their own side dish.

Have a shopping buddy

Let kids participate in grocery shopping online or in the store. Reward them by letting them choose their favorite fruit or maybe a new one.

APPENDIX J

Project Timeline

DNP Project Timeline

APPENDIX K

Data Collection Table

Planned outcomes and measurements

Summary of Planned Variables/Measurements/Assessments & Analyses								
Variable Name (Definition)	Baseline	4 weeks	8 weeks	12 weeks	Source	How it will be measured? Level of measurement	Why used in project	How it will be analyzed/used in analysis?
SSMP tracking use					Parental response from PM text	Yes/No 1=Yes- for 3 or more tracks in SSMP 0=No- for < 2 tracks per day	Intervention continuity level	Average and percentage; Paired t test at P=.05 at 4, 8, and 12 weeks
Age	X			X	PL at baseline	Nominal data	Demographic	Average and percentage
Weight	X	X	X	X	Scale results by PL	Pounds (lb)	Outcome measure	Average and percentage; Paired sample t test at p 0.05; control
BMI	X	X	X	X	EMR & CDC's BMI calculator	-calculated from EMR after wt & ht input; CDC's BMI calculator	Outcome measure	Average and percentage; Paired sample t test at p 0.05; control
Waist circumference	X	X	X	X	Measuring tape results By PL	Inches (in) via measuring tape	Outcome measure	Average and percentage; Paired sample t test at p 0.05; control
Self-esteem	X		X	X	Pre and post survey completed by participants	10 questions with: Very True:3, True:2, Not True: 1, Definitely Not True:0; Scoring is the addition of all questions. ↑ score, ↑ self-esteem	Outcome measure	Average and percentage; Paired sample t test at p 0.05; control
Parent survey	X		X	X	Survey prepared by PL	-total number of items reported per day	Process measure	Avg days per week of fruit, veggies, water, exercise and SSMP use

Note. PJ= project leader; EMR=electronic medical record; CI=confidence interval; wt=weight; &=and; ht=height; avg=averages;

APPENDIX L

Results

Table 2

<i>Body Mass Index Results (lbs/ins²)</i>				
	1st	2nd	3rd	4th
	32.32	31.8	31.8	32.5
	36.98	37.1	37.9	39.5
	29.46	30.6	30.5	30.8
	24.91	24.9	25	24.3
	25.85	26.2	27	27.2
	27.63	28.1	29	29.8
	24.8	24.8	25.3	25.8
	25.18	25.3	24.9	25
	28.11	28.8	28.3	28.2
	28.37	28	28	28.8
	22.07	21.5	21.2	22
	30.94	30.4	30.9	31.3
	25.54	26.2	25.5	26.9
	29.56	29.6	29.3	29.8
Mean	27.98	28.09286	28.18571	28.70714
SD	3.786326	3.810202	4.007658	4.267672

Table 3

Body Mass Index % Results

	1st	2nd	3rd	4th
	99	99	99	99
	99	99	99	99
	99	99	99	99
	96	96	96	95
	98	98	99	99
	99	99	99	99
	97	98	97	98
	96	96	96	96
	99	99	99	99
	98	98	98	98
	97	96	95	95
	99	99	99	99
	98	98	98	98
	99	99	99	99
Mean	98.07143	98.07143	98	98
SD	1.141139	1.206666	1.414214	1.519109

Table 4

Weight Results(lbs)

	1st	2nd	3rd	4th
	182.5	179.5	179.5	183.5
	205.5	206	210.5	219.5
	158.5	164.5	164	165.5
	126.5	126.5	127	123.5
	128	129.5	133.5	134.5
	141.5	144	148.5	152.5
	127	127	129.5	132
	120.5	121	119	119.5
	134.5	138	135.5	135
	140.5	138.5	138.5	142.5
	102	99.5	98	101.5
	138	135.5	138	139.5
	104	106.5	103.9	109.5
	129.5	129.5	128.5	130.5
Mean	138.4643	138.9643	139.5643	142.0714
SD	27.96733	28.0648	29.30549	30.73451

Table 5*Waist Circumference Results (inches)*

	1st	2nd	3rd	4th
	42	41	39	39.5
	45	44.5	44	44
	38	38	37	35.5
	35	35	34	32.5
	36	33	36	34
	37	36	37	34.5
	32	32	31.5	32
	31	30	29	29
	38	38	38	36.5
	36	35.5	34	35
	32	30	29	28.5
	36	35	35.5	34.5
	32	30	28	30
	33.5	32.5	32	33
Mean	35.96429	35.03571	34.57143	34.17857
SD	3.982965	4.294291	4.445642	4.097875

Table 6*Self-Esteem Results*

	1st	2nd	3rd
		21	18
		20	20
		26	21
		23	25
		18	22
		16	17
		20	9
		9	9
		15	15
		16	18
		18	16
		21	25
		28	21
		23	17
Mean		19.57143	18.07143
SD		4.831217	4.906264

Note. Low self-esteem (10), Moderate self-esteem (26); High self-esteem (30)

Table 7

<i>Nutrition</i>											
Fruit	Vegetables						Water				
	1st	2nd	3rd	1st	2nd	3rd	1st	2nd	3rd		
		1	1	1	1	1	1	4	4	4	4
		1	1	1	1	1	1	2	4	6	6
		3	3	3	1	1	1	2	4	4	4
		1	3	3	1	3	3	4	4	6	6
		1	1	1	1	3	3	6	4	4	4
		1	5	1	1	3	3	6	6	4	4
		3	3	3	3	3	3	4	2	4	4
		3	3	3	3	3	3	6	4	4	4
		1	3	1	1	1	3	4	6	6	6
		1	1	1	3	1	1	4	0	2	2
		3	1	1	3	3	3	2	2	4	4
		1	3	3	0	1	1	8	8	8	8
		1	3	3	1	1	1	8	8	8	8
		1	3	3	1	1	1	8	8	8	8
Frequencies servings							Frequencies cups				
0	0	0	0	0.071429	0	0	0	0	0	0.071429	0
1	0.714286	0.357143	0.5	0.642857	0.571429	0.5	2	0.214286	0.142857	0.071429	0.071429
3	0.285714	0.571429	0.5	0.285714	0.428571	0.5	4	0.357143	0.428571	0.5	0.5
5	0	0.071429	0	0	0	0	6	0.214286	0.142857	0.214286	0.214286
7 or more	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0.214286	0.214286	0.214286	0.214286

Table 8

Exercise (daily)

1st	2nd	3rd
20	20	20
20	20	45
10	31	10
31	45	45
31	45	45
20	20	45
20	31	45
20	45	20
20	20	31
31	20	31
45	31	45
10	20	10
20	20	20
20	20	20

Note. Minutes of exercise per day, ranges include 0, 10-15 min, 20-30 min, 31-40 min, 45 or more min

Table 9

SSMP App use (daily)

Baseline	8 weeks	12 weeks
0	2	8
0	0	4
0	2	2
0	6	8
0	4	4
0	4	0
0	2	4
0	6	4
0	0	0
0	4	2
0	2	0
0	2	2
0	6	4
0	6	4

Note. Number of tracked items into electronic application, ranges 0-1, 2-3, 4-5, 6-7, or 8 or more